

A Study of Achievement Motivation Among Employees of Public and Private Sector

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Abstract:- The private sector has unlocked a plethora of work opportunities, which has greatly aided society. The benefits of private sector employment often include higher income, more prospects for growth, and better benefits in the form of insurance coverage, vacation time, and annual bonuses, which have piqued the interest of youth. Working in the private sector gives you more flexibility in terms of hiring and firing staff, budgeting, and purchasing work-related items as compared to public sector. However, there is fierce competition for labor/employees when it comes to retain them. Businesses all over the world are trying to expand and fill new positions. From a human resource standpoint, the organization is under a lot of pressure to keep their most talented employees and give them with the finest benefits possible for the long term benefit of the company. HR's difficult duty is to keep the right people in the proper jobs while simultaneously realizing that employees are also business owners. Employees must be hired, taught, and polished before being assigned to a task, which is a costly process in and of it. When a person leaves a job due of dissatisfaction, it is a loss for both the individual and the employer. Keeping above experiences in mind researcher has planned to investigate the role of Achievement Motivation in Public as well as Private sector.

Keywords:- Achievement Motivation, Public Sector, Private Sector, Employee Motivation, Work Experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world where it is true with high job mislaying due to dismissal and retrenchment to create an inclined organization, it is also notable for organizations to prevent loses of potential workforce due to decreasing job satisfaction and lack of motivation at workplace to continue their job with the organization for longtime. Here the role of Human Resource is to regularly work towards alignment of aspirations of the employee with the goals of the organization. This objective can be achieved by creating inspiring work environment which promotes and addresses employee need for growth and development. These factors although complex in nature and as they could not be addressed for individual employee basis as it may vary case to case it is important for HR to explore the common areas of intersection. Job

satisfaction or employee motivation is studied not just to handle the turnover but also there are other adverse effects of dissatisfaction like absenteeism, low performance, lower morale, low contribution to the team, less coordination, less orientation towards organizational objective these could affect the organization capacity to compete in the highly competitive business environment. Hence the HR has to induce an organizational environment and promote organizational culture which takes in to consideration of the prevailing need. Motivated employees can lead to increased productivity and allow an organization to achieve higher levels of output .Motivation is the driving force by which humans achieve their goals .It is the inspiration we live and breathe for, inspiring the spirit for innovation. Achievement Motivation when an individual understands that he is responsible for the outcome of a project, when he anticipates explicit knowledge of the findings that will define his success or failure, and when there is some risk, i.e., ambiguity about the outcome of his labour, motivation to succeed kicks in. The purpose of achievement-oriented activity is to succeed, to do well in comparison to a standard of excellence or to competitors for the same. By recognizing the terms achievement and motivation individually, the phrase achievement motivation may be defined. Competence is referred to as achievement (a condition or quality of effectiveness, ability, sufficiency, or success). The instigation and goal of behaviour are referred to as motivation. As a result, achievement motivation can be described as the cause and direction of competence-relevant behaviour, or why and how people strive for success and avoid failure. When an individual expects that his performance will be judged in reference to some standard of excellence, achievement motivation, also known as the need for achievement and abbreviated n Achievement, is a crucial antecedent of aspiration, effort, and persistence. Achievement-oriented behaviour is a term used to describe this type of behaviour. In basic terms, it's a desire to succeed that originates from within and plays a critical part in task completion, self-satisfaction, and selffulfillment.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pratibha Sood (2007) examined the impact of family structure on emotional competence, achievement motivation and coping mechanisms among urban middle class preadolescents. The subject were 102 preadolescents (42 from

father absent families and 60 from two parent in act homes) drawn from the middle class English medium schools of cities of Hyderabad and secunderaba.

Prashad (2007) studied the correlation between level of aspiration and achievement in relation to gender, cast, and found that gender and achievement of students did not have interactive effects on level of aspiration. He also found that the high achievers students had higher aspirations level in comparison to low achievers students.

Veena Prajapati (2009) Studied that girls have more achievement motivation then boys.

N. Acharya and S. Joshi (2009) studied the influence of parent’s education on achievement motivation of adolescents. Sample consisted of 200 male and female adolescents of class 11th and 12 th (thirteen to nineteen years) studying in different schools of varansi city.

Rama and Nirmala Devi (2011) found that the achievement motivation of rural and urban students differed significantly from one another.

Neha Acharya and Shobhna Joshi (2011) investigated the relationship between achievement motivation and parental support and to examine the gender differences in parental support. The sample for the present study consisted of 500 adolescents in the age group of 16 to 18 years from Varanasi city who were enrolled in class 11th and 12th. The result indicted a positive correlation between achievement motivation and parental system. Girls were sensitive to parental support as compared to boys. The study revealed that parental support for their children seems to have strong influence on achievement motivation.

T.C. Gyanoni (1984) found that boys who were very motivated to accomplish were intropunitive.

Objectives :

On the basis of above studies researcher has done efforts to study the achievement motivation patterns in corporate as well as public sector. For this purpose following objective has been formulated-

- To study the level of achievement motivation among the employees of public as well as private sector.

Hypothesis:

It is hypothesized that-

- There will be no significant pattern found among the respondents of Public as well as Private Sector.
- Background variables like gender, work experience and salary packages will not effect achievement motivation for both the groups.

III. METHOD AND MATERIAL

Target Population: A target population is a subset of the population with comparable characteristics who are identified as the intended audience for a product, advertisement, or study. It's a subset of the entire universe of people who have been chosen as the objective audience. In this research work target population area) Executives and above cadre employees of NTPC, Northern Coalfields Limited serving in Singrauli district. b) Executives and above cadre employees of Hindalco, Sassan Power. ESSAR power, LANCO and Grasim Chemical Division serving in Singrauli district.

The study was conducted on the employees of Public and Private Sector in Singrauli and Sonebhadra district. The sample size of the population was 200 which are further categorized as :

- **100 employees of Public Sector**
- **100 employees of Private Sector**

Achievement Motivation Scale:

This scale has been constructed by Smith R I(2015). Smith R I is professor and department chair in counseling and educational psychology at Texas university. He is also the coordinator of the PhD Programme in counselor education. Dr. Smith is the executive director of the international association of marriage and family counseling and 63rd president of the American counseling of association. He has developed this scale to measure the achievement motivation consisting of 56 items in five point measurement scale. Always to never The reliability of scale is 9.6 and its validity is .72

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result of research is the key factor of the thesis. Fruitful and directional results provide smooth path to researcher to conclude the findings. Have efforts have been made to clarify the result in various ways, such as background variables and it impact on achievement motivation and job satisfaction. Similarly the impact of achievement motivation on job satisfaction and impact of job satisfaction on achievement motivation have been seen Vice Vs Versa.

Table 1 Gender and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

	Male		Female	
	Public	Private	Public	Private
Mean	194.44	195.06	187.96	200.23

S.D.	35.543	25.665	32.042	31.465
N	72	65	28	35
T	-0.12		-1.52	

Fig.1 Gender and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

Table 1 represents the level of Achievement Motivation according to different gender. Gender is categorized in two categories that is Male and Female. It has been calculated that mean of Males has been found 194.4 in Public sector and 195.06 in Private sector while in Females the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 187.96 in Public sector and 200.23 in Private sector.

Table 2 Work Experience and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

	Public			Private			t
	Mean	N	SD	Mean	N	SD	
0 – 5	204.72	39	36.201	209.40	50	26.319	-0.71
5 – 10	188.13	30	30.761	192.86	21	30.020	-0.55
10- 15	173.58	12	26.756	180.43	14	19.049	-0.76
15 – 20	160.75	4	6.752	167.50	4	5.00	-1.60
20 – 25	172.50	8	11.019	181.78	9	7.563	-2.04**
25 and above	218.43	7	39.866	167.50	2	3.536	1.72

Note :** Significant at .05 level

Fig. 2 : Work Experience and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

Above mentioned table 2 represents the level of Achievement Motivation according to work experience. Work experience is categorized in four categories that is 0-5, 5-10, 10-15, 15-20, 20-25 and 25 and above years. It has been calculated that mean of respondents of work experience group 0-5 has been found 204.72 and 36.201 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found higher with mean 209.40 and SD 26.319. Mean of respondents of work experience group 5-10 has been found 188.13 and 30.761 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found higher with mean 192.86 and SD 30.020. Mean of respondents of work experience group 10-15 has been found 173.58 and 26.756 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of

achievement motivation was found higher with mean 180.43 and SD 19.049.

Mean of respondents of work experience group 15-20 has been found 160.75 and 6.752 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found higher with mean 167.50 and SD 5. Mean of respondents of work experience group 20-25 has been found 172.50 and 11.019 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found higher with mean 181.78 and SD 7.56. Mean of respondents of work experience group 25 and above has been found 218.43 and 39.866 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found higher with mean 167.50 and SD 3.53.

Table 3 Salary Packages and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

	Public			Private			T
	Mean	N	SD	Mean	N	SD	
5 – 10	213.80	10	42.392	212.06	32	25.578	0.16
10- 15	200.93	27	34.788	215.14	14	27.881	-1.32
15 – 20	195.86	29	30.947	189.70	23	20.973	0.82
20 – 25	174.0	25	28.617	174.50	8	20.577	-0.05
25and above	185.56	9	32.373	179.57	23	20.520	0.63

Fig. 3 : Salary Packages and Pattern of Achievement Motivation

Above mentioned table 3 represents the level of Achievement Motivation according to salary packages. Salary is categorized in four categories i.e. 5-10, 10-15, 15-20,20-25 and 25 and above lacs. It has been calculated that mean of respondents of at a package of 5-10 has been found 213.80 and 42.392 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 212.06 and SD 25.578. Mean of respondents of at a salary package of 10-15 has been found 200.93 and 34.788 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 215.14 and SD 27.881.

Mean of respondents at a Salary Package of 15-20 has been found 195.86 and 30.947 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 189.70 and SD 20.973.

Mean of respondents at a Salary Package of 20-25 has been found 174.0 and 28.617 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 174.50 and SD 20.577.

Mean of respondents at a Salary Package of 25 lacs and above has been found 185.56 and 32.373 SD in Public sector while in Private sector the level of achievement motivation was found with mean 185.56 and SD 20.520.

V. CONCLUSION

Present study has been designed to investigate the Comparative analysis of Achievement Motivation in employees of public and private sector. It is the key factor of any employee which motivates people to perform better at their workplace. If an individual is not motivated in his/her job, it creates tension, anxiety and other negative traits in personality. Although all organizations do efforts to create better opportunities and best situation for their employees yet in private sector a new fashion of switching the job has taken place now a days. Most of the private sector employees despite of getting a high salary package remains dissatisfied and a frequent pattern of job hopping can be observed in them. Due to such behavior pattern the organizations suffer and the productivity of the organization downfall. Whereas in Public sector slow promotional aspect, sense of job security and a monotonous work routine also affects motivation and satisfaction for their job.

In this methodology 200 people were chosen as sample i.e. 100 employees from Public sector and 100 employees from Private sector. The data was collected through a questionnaire based on scale of achievement motivation. Further an analysis of the obtained data has been done and on the basis of finding/results conclusion is being given here:

- First of all Achievement motivation of the employees has been analyzed on the basis of gender, Salary Package and Work experience.
- Gender has no significant contribution for achievement motivation in either Public or Private sectors.

- Salary Package has showed significant role for achievement motivation.
- Achievement motivation was found greater in the respondents of Private sector.
- The respondents of both the sectors have showed similar pattern in regard to work experience.

On the basis of above findings it can be stated that salary packages and work experience of respondents have showed significant impact on achievement motivation, whereas gender of respondents shows no significant importance on achievement motivation.

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